

Investigating the Use of Technology in the Process of Teaching and Learning; A Critical Review

Ziarahman Amani^{1*}, Mujtaba Quayash²

¹English Language and Literature Department, Baghlan University

²Uzbeki Language and Literature Department, Baghlan University

Accepted June 15, 2021

Published June 20, 2021

*Corresponding Author:

Ziarahman Amani,

DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4999290>

Pages: 110-118

Funding: None

Distributed under
Creative Commons CC BY 4.0

Copyright: © The Author(s)

How to cite this article (APA):

Amani, Z., & Quayash, M. (2021). Investigating the Use of Technology in the Process of Teaching and Learning; A Critical Review. *North American Academic Research*, 4(6), 110-118. doi:<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4999290>

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

and instructors use some kinds of technology. It has been pointed out in many studies that the use of technology incorporates as well as improve language learning. As Murphy, DePasquale, & McNamara (2003), mentioned that technology must be used as significant part of learning by learners in their learning process because it is an effective tool for learners. The utilization of technology should be modeled by instructors for supporting curriculum where the true use of technology could be increased by learners in learning their language skills.

E-learning, is better and more useful than traditional approach but, in some cases, traditional method is better provided that we have no access to technologies and electronic devices. Traditional classroom includes lectures, note taking and explanations and some kind of instructions using white and blackboard. As a result of rapid

ABSTRACT

In this review, two articles have been reviewed critically which discusses the using of technology in the process of teaching and learning to find out the effects of e-learning and sub-categories such as: Internet; Web-based English language learning, and computer-assisted language learning (CALL)? In addition, the study is conducted to find out answers to the following two questions that how potential contributions of using technology incorporate in teaching English language to medical students? And how integration of e-learning enhances students' learning and increases the effectiveness of teachers' instruction? Two articles have been included and critically reviewed. The first one is the effects of e-learning on language learning and the second article been discussed and reviewed critically is the incorporating e-learning in teaching English language to the students of medical. First, both papers are summarized, then the highlights of the studies are reviewed, and finally the findings of both papers are reviewed critically. The findings indicated that technological tools lead the students to be independent learners. Besides, it provides learners with authentic inputs which motivates them to the language proficiency. Furthermore, e-learning activities increase students' motivation to the class content.

Keywords: TECKNOLOGY, PROCESS OF TEACHING AND LEARNING. COMPUTER ASSISTED LANGUAGE LEARNING

Introduction

In the process of learning outside or inside the class, the use of technology is considered as an important part. Usually, in language classes learners

development in technology, traditional methods have changed concerning the development. A study by Patel (2013), stated that English language teaching methods have changed through the implementation of technology. It makes the process of teaching and learning interesting and more productive in terms of advancement which are considered as alternatives.

Summary of the articles

The reviewed journal articles entitled (Effects of E-Learning on Language Learning) written by Mohammadi, N., Ghorbani, V., & Hamidi, F. (2011) and (Incorporating E-learning in teaching English language to medical students: exploring its potential contributions) written by Navidinia, H., Bidaki, M. Z., & Hekmati, N. (2016), discussed the effects of e-learning and its sub-categories such as internet, web-based English learning and computer-assisted language learning (CALL). As well as, how different surface of human life are influenced by technology. The reviewed articles are related to the teaching of English language using technology. Whereas, Hossein Navidinia (2016), stated that how does the use of technology contribute in teaching of English language. It has been discussed that how does the integration of e-learning can enhance students' learning and how it increases the effectiveness of teachers' instruction. On the hand, the articles investigated that Is e-learning an appropriate substitute for traditional learning in language learning? which have also intended on the effects of e-learning and its components on language learning and teaching.

Summary of article 1

The first article by Mohammadi, Ghorbani, & Hamidi (2011), aimed to find the effects of e-learning and its sub-categories such as internet, web-based English learning and computer-assisted language learning (CALL) on language learning in general. It is stated that before growing, developing and prevalence of World Wide Web (www) for language teaching and learning teachers and students mostly used emails but in network-based language learning; computer-based educational activities were used by both teachers and students. The research has pointed to some important factors of e-learning which are considered very essential such as, engagement, attendance and motivation of students.

Firstly, the article provides some definition of e-learning. Next, the advantages of e-learning are evaluated such as; in e-learning the role of a teacher is only to guide and facilitate the process of learning. It indicates that e-learning is categorized as learner-centered approach. Teaching through e-learning could be very convenient for learners because they can access any-time/any-where education. E-learning provides interesting games and entertained learning. In addition, lessons are prepared by different professors from different phases which make learners enable to learn more than one major or specialty and many activities in e-learning; i.e. enrolment, supervision, tuition are done by internet.

As stated, e-learning comprises many advantages it has also its own disadvantages as it decreases social relations, some learners know how to use internet while others don't have much knowledge of using internet

and there also exist some technical limitations. There may be lingual/cultural differences among the learners which can hinder the process of learning and teaching. Then, the article also focuses on the effects of subparts of e-learning for example the researchers have stated that electronic devices such as television and online games can attract the learner's attention because mostly children as well as teens like sounds and images. It also discusses the Online games which is helpful for learning vocabulary and learning correct pronunciation and the use of blogs in creating competitive drills and activities.

Findings of the study

Considering the advantages and disadvantages of e-learning and traditional methods of language learning, we can determine that e-learning is better and more useful than traditional approaches. In some cases, traditional methods are better applicable where we have no access to technologies and electronic devices. For instance, in developed and developing countries where people have access to internet and electronic devices, e-learning is better to use. Whereas, in undeveloped countries where people have little knowledge of internet and computers with poor internet, they have to use traditional approaches of language learning.

Highlights of the study

The main advantage of e-learning is that it increases the engagement, attendance and motivation of students which are requisite for language learning. E-learning is a virtual English language learning environment. Since language learning is challenging and time-consuming and costs highly in some cases, by using distance education and e-learning we can reduce the amount of expenses and time.

Finally, the article tries to show the effects of e-learning and compares it with traditional approaches of language learning. It tries to explain different parts of e-learning and their effects on language learning. By the advancement of technology, the use of e-learning, electronic devices, internet, computers in teaching and learning language is a matter. The more teachers and learners get familiar with technologies, the more they can use and incorporate them with their teaching styles and these technologies provide teachers with practical and creative ideas and make them create their own eclectic methods.

Summary of article 2

This particular article is written by Hossein Navidinia, Majid Zare Bidaki, and Nargess Hekmati (2016) that entitles (Incorporating E-learning in teaching English language to medical students: exploring its potential contributions). It generally focuses on the potential contribution of the use of technology in teaching English language to medical students. A qualitative research method with an action design is applied to achieve the objectives of the study. The research is conducted in Birjand University of Medical Science where 60 medicals students have taken a general English course during the Fall Semester of 2015. The class is fully equipped with the technological tools, also internet is provided for the use of students during the sessions. In addition, a weblog has been created for exchanging the learning and teaching activities as well as evaluation of teacher and

students' peers.

In terms of research procedure and analysis, first of all, students reflected in their English language learning approach. They highlighted the use of films, internet, and e-dictionaries. Next, an integrated approach by the support of technology was applied to teach them the language using tube channel, online films, e-dictionaries, e-textbooks, and a weblog where they could watch and upload educational videos to have feedback from the teacher and their peers. Whereas, by the end of the term, an open-ended questionnaire distributed to the learners through which they reflected to the innovative course. The answers from the content of the questionnaire analyzed and resulted the findings of this article and its discussion.

Basically, the research indicated that e-learning improves learners language proficiency and assists the instructors to create a dynamic learning and teaching space. The use of technological tools such as e-dictionaries, e-textbooks, related video tape, internet access, and integrated tasks, not only enable the learners to perform language skills, but also provide them the opportunity to practice the language anytime/anywhere. Accordingly, the learners reflected that this integrated method of teaching and learning by the support of technological tools provided authentic input and motivated them to be independent learners.

In terms of the research problem, the article demonstrate that human's life has been affected by technology, however teaching and learning especially language teaching and learning is one of the sequences of its emergence. Currently, the use of technological tools in teaching and learning English language really contributes to a significant influence. One of these technological tools is e-learning that this research attempts to determine its potential contribution in teaching English language to medical students.

In terms of research questions and research objectives, the authors followed two correlated objectives: examining the potential contribution of the use of technology in teaching English language to medical students, and enhancing students' language proficiency and facilitating the teaching process through e-learning. Whereas, in terms of research questions, the researchers followed the study by two research questions How potential contributions of using technology incorporates in teaching English language to medical students? How integration of e-learning enhances students' learning and increases the effectiveness of teachers' instruction? to achieve the research objectives.

The literatures in this article concentrates on what e-learning is basically. According to Zehry and Halder (2011), e-learning is the use of information technology or internet for learning and teaching. It provides another opportunity in educational arenas that learning and teaching could happen anytime/anywhere. Whereas, Chryso (2011) claimed that e-learning has made it much easier for the learners to access and share knowledge and information. Whereas, it can be summarized that technology facilitated every surface of our current life, with

the development of it, a new revolution arisen in educational setting which refers to e-learning.

Findings of the study

The findings of the study reflected that e-learning functions as an autonomous model of teaching and learning which engages students to deal with multimedia, internet, mobile, e-dictionaries, as well as support teachers to provide authentic language input. In addition, the use of e-learning and technological tools leads the students to be independent learners. Also, it provides learners with authentic inputs which motivates them to the language proficiency. The findings also illustrate that technology provides the opportunity for integrated learning which fosters learners four skills of the language. Likewise, e-learning enables the learners to be familiar with online sources, have access to the content, teacher, and their peers anytime/anywhere.

Highlights of the study

As the finding of the study highlighted the flexibility of the e-learning approach, there are several online courses available that students can take it from home. Technology has made it possible for teachers to integrate different teaching methods base on the needs of learners (Dashtestani, 2014). As well as, incorporating language teaching with technology enables the learners to be independent. Therefore, teachers introduce some online sources so that students engage and practice the language outside the class.

In sum, the research exposed to the benefits of incorporating technology in teaching English language to the students of medical. Changing the approach by applying the e-learning is an evidence that students enhanced language proficiency, and it ultimately supported teaching process. As well as, the findings of this research proposed that e-learning be incorporated by English language programs to medical students. In addition, e-learning activities provide authentic language input for the learners. In addition, technological tools lead the learners to be more independent learner. It also supports the teachers to facilitate the students with authentic language input so that they could practice the language outside the class.

Critical review of articles

Both of these articles investigated the use ICT (Information Communication Technology) particularly e-learning such as CALL, Electronic devices, Online games, Internet and multimedia, and Blogs in terms of new approaches to teach a foreign language. In addition, it is demonstrated that the widely use of ICTs have impacted various part of the life more specifically the education and the foreign language teaching and learning. In terms of appropriateness, the importance of technology caused that these types of articles should have been investigated while it is supporting teaching and learning in different regions with different range of application. As we read through these two articles, it is highly supporting the foreign language teaching and learning platforms.

Since e-learning is a consequently emerging topic whiten the language learning and teaching context, the North American Academic Research, 4(6) | June 2021 | <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4999290> Monthly Journal by TWASP, USA | 114

researchers extended the ideas related the use of these technological approaches and varying it into different contexts. We think that it is really supporting language teaching and learning. For instance, it reduces the learning cost, provides anywhere/anytime education, motivates the learners. We do agree that it also facilitates a variety of cooperative language learning activities since language is learned through interactive cooperation.

As hints, the first article entitled (Effects of E-Learning on Language Learning) written by Neda Mohammadia, Vahid Ghorbanib, Farideh Hamidiab (2011), discussed what is e-learning, advantages of e-learning, disadvantages of e-learning, part of e-learning and their effects on language learning such as Electronic devices, Online games, Internet and multimedia, and Blogs. Whereas, the second article entitled (Incorporating E-learning in teaching English language to medical students: exploring its potential contributions) written by Hossein Navidinia, Majid Zare Bidaki, Nargess Hekmati (2016) also discussed that e-learning could enhance students' language proficiency and facilitate the teaching process. Therefore, we can elaborate that both of these articles discuss similar ideas relating to e-learning and foreign language learning.

In terms of the strengths, both of these articles aimed to investigate on the effects of e-learning and sub-categories such as: Internet; Web-based English language learning, and computer-assisted language learning (CALL) as well as examining the potential contribution of the use of technology in teaching English language while it is investigated appropriately. Indeed, the use ICT enhances the students' language proficiency and facilitates the teaching process through e-learning. However, these two articles are guided by main research questions which intends that they evaluated similar outcome by using different research approaches within different context. Therefore, the overall findings illustrate that e-learning is highly supported for foreign language teaching and learning and following the research questions the objectives of the study is achieved.

As it is also clarified in the second article that technology facilitated every surface of our today's life, with the development of it, a new revolution arisen in educational setting which refers to e-learning. Similarly, Zehry and Halder (2011) claimed that e-learning is the use of information technology or internet for learning and teaching. It provides another opportunity in educational arenas that learning and teaching could happen anytime/anywhere. Whereas, Chryso (2011) claimed that e-learning has made it much easier for the learners to access and share knowledge and information. All of these hints clarify that the potential use of e-learning supports foreign language teaching and learning in a variety of ways.

Moreover, the first article discusses on how to transit the traditional approaches of language teaching and learning into technological-integrated approaches. Therefore, Pitler, Hubbell, Kuhn and Malenoski (2007) claimed that technology has made it possibility for teachers to integrate different teaching methods based on the needs of the students. This flexibility in terms of teaching methods and engaging technological tools to facilitate learning, motivates students to interact more effectively. It also supports teachers to develop authentic

teaching materials in order to achieve the learning objectives. In this regard, Chhabra (2012) also argued that it is the teacher's responsibility to change the methods based on the needs and demands of the students. Therefore, teaching English language by the support of technology became a prominent phenomenon that changed the traditional ways of teaching and learning.

In brief, using technology, more specifically e-learning functions to provide authentic input and enhances learning and teaching language. The literatures in these two articles indicated that there are many researches that have been evaluated in learning and teaching English through e-learning approaches. Whereas, Avanaki, Sadeghi, and Akbari (2014) claimed that teaching general English language in Iranian universities did not promote students' language proficiency. As far as, these particular researches concentrated to explore the potential contribution of the use of technology in teaching English language and how to use ICT or e-learning in language education.

Article 1		Article 2	
Methods	Review of Literatures	Methods	Qualitative/ Action Research Design
RQ/RO	<p>Is e-learning an appropriate substitute for traditional learning in language learning?</p> <p>The study investigates on the effects of e-learning and sub-categories such as: Internet; Web-based English language learning, and computer-assisted language learning (CALL)</p>	RQ/RO	<p>How potential contributions of using technology incorporate in teaching English language to medical students?</p> <p>How integration of e-learning enhances students' learning and increases the effectiveness of teachers' instruction?</p>
Findings	<p>E-learning is better and more useful than traditional approaches.</p> <p>E-learning tools engages students' participation in teaching and learning circumstances.</p> <p>In some cases, traditional methods are better applicable where we have no access to technologies and electronic devices.</p>	Findings	<p>Technological tools lead the students to be independent learners.</p> <p>It provides learners with authentic inputs which motivates them to the language proficiency.</p> <p>E-learning activities increase students' motivation to the class content.</p>

Chart 1 Summarizing critics of Both Articles

Conclusion

The findings indicated that using e-learning is better and is considered more useful than traditional method. Furthermore, students are encouraged and will have an active participation in the process of teaching and learning while e-learning tools are used. Besides, the technological tools lead the students to be independent it provides learners with authentic inputs which motivates them to the language proficiency. Moreover, e-learning activities increase students' motivation to the class content but in some cases, traditional methods are better applicable where we have no access to technologies and electronic devices

References

1. Chryso P. Designing a pedagogically grounded e-learning activity. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*. 2012 Jan 1;31:841-5.
2. Hine GS. The importance of action research in teacher education programs. Hine, G. S. C. (2013). 23(2), 151-163. <http://www.iier.org.au/iier23/hine.html>
3. Makhdoom N, Khoshhal KI, Algaidi S, Heissam K, Zolaly MA. 'Blended learning' as an effective teaching and learning strategy in clinical medicine: a comparative cross-sectional university-based study. *Journal of taibah university medical sciences*. 2013 Apr 1;8(1):12-7.
4. Malmir M, Zare M, Sarikhani R, Mansouri V, Salari M. The impact of using E-Portfolio on nursing students' learning in physiology course. *Future of medical education journal*. 2016 Jun 1;6(2):9-12.
5. Murphy KL, DePasquale R, McNamara E. Meaningful Connections. *Young Children*. 2003 Nov.
6. Patel C. Use of multimedia technology in teaching and learning communication skill: An analysis. Pitler H, Hubbell ER, Kuhn M, Malenoski K. Using. *International Journal of Advancements in Research & Technology*. 2013 Jul;2(7):116-23.
7. Stringer ET. *Action research in education*. Upper Saddle River, NJ: Pearson Prentice Hall; 2008.
8. Mohammadi, N., Ghorbani, V., & Hamidi, F. (2011). Effects of e-learning on language learning. *Procedia Computer Science*, 3, 464–468. doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2010.12.078.
9. Navidinia, H., Bidaki, M. Z., & Hekmati, N. (2016). Incorporating E-learning in teaching English language to medical students: Exploring its potential contributions. *Medical Journal of the Islamic Republic of Iran*, 30(1), 1–8.

Ziarahman Amani is Master of Education. He is a qualified senior EFL lecturer at Baghlan University, Faculty of Literature and Humanities.

Email: ziamozia19@gmail.com

Mujtaba Quyash is Turkish Language and Literature. He is a qualified senior lecturer at Baghlan University, Department of Uzbek language and Literature Faculty of Literature and Humanities.

Email: mujtabaquyash14@gmail.com

© 2021 by the authors. Author/authors are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in above pages. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

